

Investigating the Efficiency of Magnetized Biopolymer Beads in Extracting Small Plastics from Low-Flow Water Systems

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ABSTRACT

Small kinds of plastics, such as micro- or macroplastics, are common environmental pollutants that threaten ecosystems and human health, with an estimated 10–40 million metric tons entering the environment annually and projected to double by 2040 (Thompson et al., 2024). Due to their synthetic and non-degradable nature, small plastics persist in aquatic environments and accumulate in food chains, posing risks of endocrine disruption, inflammation, and bioaccumulation of toxic chemicals (Ziani et al., 2023). This study investigates whether magnetized biopolymer beads, sodium alginate beads embedded with iron-oxide nanoparticles, can serve as a low-cost and scalable method for extracting small plastics from low-flow water systems.

A quasi-experimental design was used to test four bead concentrations (10, 20, 30, and 40 beads) in a simulated low-flow water system. Small plastic extraction efficiency was measured through filtration and manual particle counting, while bead stability was evaluated across eight reuse cycles. Results showed that extraction efficiency increased with bead concentration, rising from 0.33% with 10 beads to 7.67% with 40 beads. Statistical analysis indicated that only the increase from 10 beads to higher concentrations was significant ($p = 0.019–0.001$), while additional increases beyond 20 beads showed no statistically significant differences. The beads maintained magnetic responsiveness and structural integrity throughout repeated reuse cycles. These findings demonstrate that magnetized alginate beads can capture small plastics in low-flow water systems, confirming the concept's feasibility. However, the relatively low removal efficiency suggests that further improvements, such as surface modification or polymer functionalization, are necessary to enhance adsorption and support practical environmental applications.

INTRODUCTION

Plastic pollution has emerged as one of the most pressing environmental crises of the twenty-first century. Globally, an estimated 10 to 40 million metric tons of small plastics and microplastics enter the environment each year, and under business-as-usual scenarios, this figure is projected to double by 2040 (Thompson et al., 2024). Plastic debris is now found across virtually every ecosystem, from the deepest ocean trenches to mountain snowfields, making it a ubiquitous and persistent contaminant (Ziani et al., 2023). At the national level, the Philippines ranks among the world's top plastic polluters. Studies documenting microplastic concentrations in Manila Bay's river mouths (Osorio et al., 2021) and in major river systems such as the Cagayan de Oro River (Gabriel et al., 2023) confirm that aquatic environments across the archipelago are heavily contaminated. Locally, surveys of low-flow coastal and estuarine habitats in Bulacan and surrounding provinces of Central Luzon have revealed microplastic accumulation in sediments and aquatic organisms, underscoring the regional relevance of developing cost-effective remediation strategies (Gacilos et al., 2024).

Small plastics are produced primarily through the physical and photochemical degradation of larger polymer products such as bags, bottles, and synthetic textiles. Polymers, by design, resist degradation and are engineered for stability and durability; rather than fully breaking down, they fragment into progressively smaller pieces that persist in the environment for

hundreds to thousands of years (Bacha et al., 2023; Lai, 2022). These fragments, typically less than 5 mm in their largest dimension, are too small to be captured by most conventional wastewater treatment systems (European Environment Agency, 2022). Moreover, as small plastics age in aquatic environments, they adsorb toxic pollutants such as heavy metals and persistent organic compounds from the surrounding water, increasing their hazard potential (Kye et al., 2023). Ingestion by aquatic organisms, from plankton and bivalves to commercially important fish species, allows these contaminant-laden particles to biomagnify through the food chain, ultimately reaching human consumers (Bonifacio et al., 2022; Similatan et al., 2023; Benaires et al., 2025).

Low-flow water systems such as rivers, lakes, ponds, drainage canals, and mangrove areas are especially vulnerable to small plastic accumulation. Reduced water velocity allows particles to settle and concentrate in sediments, creating persistent hotspots of contamination that affect local biodiversity and pose long-term ecological risks (Gacilos et al., 2024). The U.S. Environmental Protection Agency recognizes low-flow conditions as a critical factor in contaminant fate and transport, noting that pollutants accumulate disproportionately in low-flow zones and can cause severe stress on aquatic ecosystems (U.S. EPA, 2025). In the Philippine context, most affected communities lack access to advanced water treatment infrastructure, reinforcing the need for low-cost, scalable, and locally deployable remediation technologies.

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Existing approaches to small plastic removal, including coagulation-flocculation, membrane filtration, and electrocoagulation, have demonstrated varying degrees of effectiveness but are generally energy-intensive, prone to clogging, and risk generating secondary pollutants through toxic chemical residues (Kim et al., 2021; Rasheed et al., 2023; Badawi et al., 2025). These limitations highlight the urgent need for sustainable alternatives. Biopolymer-based materials have recently attracted considerable attention as eco-friendly adsorbents for water treatment. Among these, sodium alginate, a natural polysaccharide derived from brown seaweed, offers exceptional adsorption properties through its hydroxyl (-OH) and carboxyl (-COOH) functional groups, which facilitate electrostatic interactions, hydrogen bonding, and ion exchange with a wide range of contaminants (Rafiee, 2023; Rahman et al., 2024). When combined with iron-oxide nanoparticles, alginate beads acquire magnetic properties that allow simple and efficient recovery from treated water using an external magnet, eliminating the need for costly separation equipment (Vohl et al., 2024; Cao et al., 2024).

Despite growing interest in magnetized biopolymers for wastewater treatment, most existing studies have been conducted under high-flow or controlled laboratory conditions, leaving a critical gap in knowledge regarding their performance in low-flow environments, precisely the settings where small plastic accumulation is most problematic. This study aims to address that gap by investigating the efficiency of magnetized alginate biopolymer beads in extracting small plastics from a simulated low-flow water system. By examining how bead concentration affects removal efficiency and evaluating bead reusability and structural integrity across repeated extraction cycles, this research provides baseline experimental data to support the development of sustainable, low-cost solutions for small plastic pollution in aquatic environments. The study is particularly relevant to communities in the Philippines and similar developing nations where affordable and scalable water remediation tools are most urgently needed.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Prevalence, Transport, and Ecological Toxicity of Small Plastics in Aquatic Environments

Small plastics are ubiquitous in aquatic environments worldwide, and their distribution is closely linked to water flow dynamics. Research consistently shows that low-flow environments, including mangrove areas, estuaries, river mouths, and shallow coastal habitats, serve as accumulation zones where reduced water velocity causes plastic particles to settle and concentrate in sediments (Gacilos et al., 2024; Osorio et al., 2021). In Manila Bay, microplastic concentrations in surface water ranged from 1,580 to 57,665 particles per cubic meter, while sediment samples contained 386 to 1,357 particles per kilogram of dry weight, with microplastics present in all sampled river mouth sites (Osorio et al., 2021). Along the Cagayan de Oro River, concentrations were highest near the river mouth, indicating that plastic particles migrate downstream with water currents before accumulating where flows slow (Gabriel et al., 2023). This transportability means that small plastics originating in one location can spread extensively, ultimately entering marine and coastal ecosystems far from their source. Kye et al. (2023) further demonstrated that as plastics age in aquatic environments, they adsorb and concentrate toxic pollutants such as heavy metals, PCBs, and hydrophobic organic compounds from surrounding water. This aging process amplifies their toxicity and increases the danger they pose when ingested by aquatic organisms.

The ecological consequences of small plastic ingestion have been documented extensively across trophic levels in Philippine

aquatic systems. Bonifacio et al. (2022) identified 2,258 microplastic particles in sediment samples from Panguil Bay, and a further 1,495 particles within the tissues of three commercially harvested bivalve species, with *Katelysia hiantina* showing the highest accumulation. Similatan et al. (2023) found microplastics in 29 of 30 milkfish (*Chanos chanos*) samples from Butuan Bay, a prevalence rate of 97%, raising significant concerns given that milkfish is one of the most widely consumed fish species in the Philippines. Benaires et al. (2025) extended these findings to commercially sold fish in Tacloban City's wet markets, detecting plastics in all five major species analyzed and identifying polymer types including HDPE and polypropylene commonly associated with everyday plastic waste. Lahoy et al. (2025) similarly confirmed microplastic presence in 27.5% of rabbitfish (*Siganus canaliculatus*) sampled from Pujada Bay, a species commonly consumed by coastal communities. These studies collectively establish that small plastics have entered the human food chain through seafood consumption, posing risks of chronic exposure to toxic plastic-associated chemicals (Issac & Kandasubramanian, 2021). Beyond direct ingestion, small plastics disrupt feeding behavior, reduce reproductive success in aquatic organisms, and threaten ecosystem stability by altering population dynamics across multiple trophic levels. At the community level, awareness of these risks remains uneven; Angela et al. (2024) found that although young adults in Muntinlupa demonstrated general knowledge of microplastics and their health risks, actual waste separation practices remained poor, with only 41.5% consistently segregating plastic from biodegradable waste, highlighting the gap between awareness and behavioral change.

Existing Methods for Small Plastic Extraction and Their Limitations

Addressing small plastic pollution in water systems requires effective removal technologies, and numerous approaches have been explored with varying degrees of success. Kim et al. (2021) investigated a hybrid electrocoagulation and granule-activated carbon (GAC) system, achieving removal efficiency of up to 92% for particles in the 20–50 μm range. While this efficiency is impressive, the process was found to be highly energy-intensive and operationally costly, limiting its feasibility for widespread deployment in resource-constrained settings. Rasheed et al. (2023) conducted a comprehensive review of treatment technologies and concluded that although processes such as sand filtration, membrane filtration, and coagulation-flocculation can achieve high removal rates, most are either too expensive, require complex equipment, or generate secondary chemical residues that introduce new contamination risks. Duan et al. (2024) examined the interaction between microplastics and coagulants in textile wastewater, revealing that microplastics can interfere with coagulation performance by competing for binding sites, further complicating conventional treatment approaches. Badawi et al. (2025) reviewed coagulative microplastic removal from aquatic systems and emphasized that while promising, such technologies require optimization to avoid introducing additional chemicals that may be harmful to aquatic ecosystems.

These limitations, high energy demands, cost, technical complexity, and secondary pollution risks create a compelling need for simpler, greener, and more affordable alternatives. The concept of using adsorbent materials that can be deployed at low cost and recovered without complex infrastructure has gained traction as a practical solution for communities lacking access to advanced treatment facilities. Magnetic separation has been identified as a promising retrieval mechanism because it allows adsorbent beads to be rapidly collected from treated water using an external magnet, without the need for filtration equipment (Surette et al., 2023). The convergence of

biodegradable adsorbents with magnetic retrievability, as embodied by magnetized biopolymer beads, thus represents a conceptually attractive alternative to conventional methods, provided sufficient extraction efficiency can be demonstrated under relevant environmental conditions.

Biopolymer-Based and Magnetized Materials for Sustainable Water Treatment

Biopolymers have attracted growing interest as sustainable alternatives for water treatment due to their biodegradability, biocompatibility, and functional surface chemistry. Vishwakarma (2023) reviewed biopolymer-based materials for wastewater treatment and identified adsorption as the most reliable and widely applicable technique, attributing the effectiveness of biopolymers to their high surface area, abundance of reactive functional groups, and capacity for modification. Hamidon et al. (2024) specifically reviewed biopolymer-based beads for organic pollutant removal and reported that bead morphologies offer superior performance compared to powdered or film forms, owing to improved mass transfer characteristics and ease of recovery. Among biopolymers, sodium alginate has emerged as a particularly promising matrix material. Rahman et al. (2024) reviewed alginate sources, extraction methods, and applications, emphasizing its high gel-forming capacity and the role of its carboxyl (-COOH) and hydroxyl (-OH) groups in pollutant binding through electrostatic interactions, hydrogen bonding, and ion exchange. Akshaya and Nathanael (2024) demonstrated that hydrophobically associated alginates show enhanced affinity for organic and hydrophobic pollutants, suggesting that surface modification of alginate beads could substantially improve their interaction with plastic particles, which are predominantly hydrophobic polymers. Han et al. (2025) developed a polydopamine-modified sodium alginate hydrogel and demonstrated strong adsorption performance for microplastics, confirming that functional modifications can improve the affinity between alginate matrices and plastic particles. Amor et al. (2023) showed that alginate-geopolymer hybrid beads retained excellent removal efficiency even when applied to real environmental water samples, demonstrating practical applicability beyond controlled laboratory conditions.

The integration of iron oxide nanoparticles into biopolymer matrices has been studied extensively as a strategy to combine adsorption with magnetic retrievability. Vohl et al. (2024) reviewed magnetic nanoparticle designs for micro- and nanoplastic removal and found that iron-oxide-based magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) achieve rapid aggregation with plastic particles through hydrophobic interactions and electrostatic attraction, enabling effective magnetic separation even at low particle concentrations. Importantly, they noted that encapsulation of iron oxide within larger polymeric beads reduces nanoparticle leaching and maintains magnetic separability, a design feature directly relevant to the magnetized alginate bead approach. Cao et al. (2024) presented a comprehensive review of iron-oxide composites for plastic separation and degradation, documenting high first pass capture efficiencies and noting that embedding iron oxide in biopolymer matrices improves safety, increases effective particle size, and allows surface functionalization for polymer-specific ligand attachment. Divya et al. (2025) examined hybrid magnetic nanoparticles (HMNPs) with bio-based polymer shells and found that such structures can be optimized for capture in low-Reynolds-number (i.e., low-flow) conditions by maximizing hydrodynamic cross-section and surface roughness, both of which increase contact probability with small plastic particles. Surette et al. (2023) demonstrated that hydrophobically functionalized magnetic nanoparticles can extract nanoplastics from aqueous suspensions using a magnetic flow cell,

maintaining structural integrity and magnetic responsiveness through multiple extraction events without observable physical degradation. Abutu et al. (2025) further showed that ferric oxide-modified alginate beads retained structural and functional stability through multiple bioreactor cycles, providing direct evidence that iron oxide incorporation does not compromise bead durability. Bakhteeva et al. (2024) developed environmentally friendly composite magnetic particles specifically designed for microplastic extraction from water media and demonstrated effective removal rates alongside strong reusability, while also noting that practical extraction efficiency in low-flow systems depends heavily on bead size and aggregation behavior under hydrodynamic shear. Mohanransu et al. (2025) reviewed eco-friendly biopolymer composites as sustainable adsorbents for pollutant removal and identified gaps in research on applications for low-flow water bodies, where accumulated microplastics pose the greatest ecological threat. Collectively, these studies validate the rationale for using magnetized alginate biopolymer beads as a sustainable, low-cost approach to small plastic extraction, while also identifying key optimization parameters including surface functionalization, bead size, and iron oxide concentration that should be addressed in future research to improve practical extraction efficiency.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This study investigates the efficiency of magnetized biopolymer beads in removing small plastics from low-flow water systems using a small-scale experimental setup. The study aims to provide baseline data and insights that can serve as a reference for future researchers developing alternative and sustainable solutions for reducing plastic contamination in aquatic environments.

Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. Measured through filtration and manual enumeration, what is the average percentage of small plastics extracted by magnetized biopolymer beads at different bead concentrations (10, 20, 30, and 40 beads)? What is the effect of bead concentration on the percentage of small plastics removed?
2. How consistent is the extraction rate of magnetized biopolymer beads at each bead concentration, as measured by descriptive statistics (mean, variance, and standard deviation)?
3. After how many reuse cycles do magnetized biopolymer beads show a significant decline in plastic removal efficiency, using a set of 10 magnetized biopolymer beads?
4. What physical and functional changes in the 10 magnetized biopolymer beads can be observed after repeated extraction cycles, particularly with respect to extraction rate, clumping, sinking, shrinkage, swelling, bursting, and magnetic responsiveness?

HYPOTHESIS

Null Hypothesis (H₀): Magnetized biopolymer beads have no significant effect on the extraction of small plastics from low-flow water systems.

Alternative Hypothesis (H₁): Magnetized biopolymer beads have a significant effect on the extraction of small plastics from low-flow water systems.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quantitative quasi-experimental design to investigate the effectiveness of magnetized biopolymer beads in extracting small plastics from a simulated low-flow water system. A quasi-experimental approach was selected because the study compared treatment outcomes across varying bead

concentrations without random assignment or a separate control group using an alternative extraction method; rather than manipulating actual low-flow water bodies such as rivers or canals—where full control over environmental variables is not feasible—the researchers replicated the conditions of a plastic-contaminated low-flow water system on a small scale. The experimental setup consisted of four treatment groups defined by bead concentration (10, 20, 30, and 40 magnetized biopolymer beads), each tested in three independent trials, with 100 small plastic particles (polyethylene, polyethylene terephthalate, and polypropylene, $\leq 500 \mu\text{m}$) introduced per trial. Water volume, plastic concentration, temperature, stirring duration, and all other experimental conditions were held constant across trials to minimize confounding variables. The magnetized biopolymer beads were prepared by gradually dissolving 2 g of sodium alginate powder in 100 mL of water to form a homogeneous solution, separately dissolving 1 g of calcium chloride in 200 mL of water as the cross-linking bath, and pre-wetting 5 g of iron oxide powder with 10 mL of water to minimize clumping. The sodium alginate solution and the pre-wetted iron oxide were then combined and mixed thoroughly, after which the mixture was dripped through a syringe into the calcium chloride solution to initiate ionic cross-linking and form stable magnetized alginate beads. During each extraction trial, the designated number of magnetized beads was introduced into a 2-liter container of plastic-contaminated water, which was gently stirred for 20 minutes to simulate low-flow conditions. After stirring, a strong magnet was used to retrieve the beads, and the remaining water was filtered through a mesh strainer; residual plastic particles were counted manually using tweezers, and extraction efficiency was calculated as the percentage of plastics removed from each trial. A separate reusability test was conducted using a fixed set of 10 beads across eight consecutive extraction cycles, each with 100 small plastics, to evaluate whether repeated use led to any measurable decline in removal efficiency or observable physical degradation. Data collection utilized two researcher-developed observation sheets validated by content experts in grammar, statistics, and the relevant scientific field. The first sheet recorded extraction rates and descriptive statistics (mean, variance, and standard deviation) for each concentration group; the second documented quantitative and qualitative changes in bead properties—including clumping, sinking, shrinkage, swelling, bursting, and magnetic responsiveness—across reuse cycles. Statistical analysis employed descriptive statistics, one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), and post hoc Tukey tests to determine whether bead concentration significantly affected extraction efficiency, using a 90% confidence level ($\alpha = 0.10$). Throughout the experiment, all chemical and plastic residues were handled and disposed of according to institutional safety guidelines to minimize environmental contamination and ensure ethical compliance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the findings of the experiment organized according to the four research questions guiding the study. Data are interpreted in relation to existing literature to contextualize the observed results.

Table 1: Extraction Rate Efficiency Test Per Bead Concentration Results

Observation Sheet I – Extraction rate efficiency test per bead concentration.							
Bead Concentrations	Initial Amount of Small Plastics	Trial 1, Extraction Rate	Trial 2, Extraction Rate	Trial 3, Extraction Rate	Average Extraction Rate	Variance	Standard Deviation
10	100	0%	1%	0%	0.33%	0.33	0.58
20	100	6%	4%	4%	4.67%	1.33	1.15
30	100	8%	6%	8%	7.33%	1.33	1.15
40	100	10%	7%	6%	7.67%	4.33	2.08

The results for Table 1 showed a positive relationship between bead concentration and mean extraction rate. The 10-bead group yielded a mean extraction rate of 0.33%, the 20-bead group 4.67%, the 30-bead group 7.33%, and the 40-bead group 7.67%. Despite this increasing trend, the overall extraction efficiency remained low across all concentrations, with even the highest concentration failing to exceed 8% removal. One-way ANOVA revealed a statistically significant difference among the four bead concentrations ($F(3, 8) = 18.8, p < .001$), exceeding the critical F-value of 4.07 at the 90% confidence level, which led to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Post hoc Tukey comparisons confirmed that the 10-bead group differed significantly from the 20-bead group ($p = .019$), the 30-bead group ($p = .001$), and the 40-bead group ($p < .001$). However, no statistically significant differences were found between the 20- and 30-bead groups, between the 20- and 40-bead groups, or between the 30- and 40-bead groups, indicating that extraction performance plateaued beyond 20 beads.

These findings are consistent with the broader literature on magnetic adsorbent systems in water treatment, where increasing adsorbent quantity generally improves removal up to a saturation point, after which additional material yields diminishing returns (Cao et al., 2024). The low overall efficiency likely reflects the hydrophilic nature of unmodified alginate, which limits its affinity for the predominantly hydrophobic surfaces of PE, PET, and PP plastics (Akshaya & Nathanael, 2024; Han et al., 2025). This hydrophilic-hydrophobic mismatch is a recognized challenge in alginate-based adsorption systems and suggests that surface functionalization strategies such as hydrophobic coating or polymer grafting would be necessary to substantially improve performance in future iterations (Siddiqui et al., 2025; Saiyad et al., 2024).

Moreover, descriptive statistics demonstrated that extraction results were relatively consistent across trials within each concentration group. The 10-bead group recorded a standard deviation (SD) of approximately 0.58 and a variance of 0.33, indicating minimal variability. The 20-bead group showed an SD of 1.15 and a variance of 1.33, as did the 30-bead group. The 40-bead group showed slightly higher variability (SD = 2.08, variance = 4.33), which may reflect the increased complexity of bead-plastic interactions at higher concentrations. These low-to-moderate variability values confirm that the observed extraction rates represent genuine performance characteristics of the magnetized biopolymer beads rather than experimental artifacts or random fluctuation, thereby validating the reliability and replicability of the results.

Table 2: Magnetized Biopolymer Bead's Reusability Test and Physical and Functional Observation Changes Results

Observation sheet II – Magnetized biopolymer beads' reusability test and physical and functional observation changes.									
Cycles	Bead Concentration	Initial Amount of Small Plastics	Extraction Rate	Clumping	Sinking	Shrinkage	Swelling	Bursting	Magnetic Responsiveness
1	10	100	1%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	100%
2	10	100	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	100%
3	10	100	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	100%
4	10	100	3%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	100%
5	10	100	2%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	100%
6	10	100	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	100%
7	10	100	1%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	100%
8	10	100	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	100%
Average Extraction Rate			0.88%						

The reusability test conducted over eight extraction cycles using 10 magnetized biopolymer beads addressed Research Question 3. As presented in Table 2, extraction efficiencies per cycle were 1% (Cycle 1), 0% (Cycle 2), 0% (Cycle 3), 3% (Cycle 4), 2% (Cycle 5), 0% (Cycle 6), 1% (Cycle 7), and 0% (Cycle 8), yielding an overall mean extraction rate of 0.88% across cycles. Contrary to expectations of a systematic performance decline, no clear

downward trend was observed; instead, extraction rates fluctuated inconsistently at very low levels. This result indicates that there is no identifiable threshold number of cycles after which performance deteriorates significantly under the tested conditions, but it also reveals that single-bead-set reusability does not meaningfully amplify extraction efficiency over repeated use. These findings suggest that the adsorption capacity of the beads, rather than structural degradation, is the primary limiting factor in reusability.

Moreover, the examined observable physical and functional changes in the beads across the eight reuse cycles. Results were notable for their uniformity: 100% of beads (10 of 10) showed 0% clumping, 0% shrinkage, 0% swelling, 0% bursting, and 0% sinking across all cycles. Magnetic responsiveness remained intact at 100% throughout all cycles. These findings confirm that the magnetized alginate beads maintained their structural integrity and functional properties under repeated use, consistent with results reported by Surette et al. (2023) for hydrophobically functionalized magnetic nanoparticles, which similarly displayed no observable physical degradation through multiple extraction events. Abutu et al. (2025) likewise reported that ferric oxide-modified alginate beads retained structural stability through multiple bioreactor cycles. The contrast between high physical and functional stability and low extraction efficiency indicates that the primary limitation of the current formulation is adsorption capacity rather than mechanical durability, a distinction that is important for guiding future optimization efforts. As Bakhteeva et al. (2024) noted, effective particle recovery does not automatically translate to high extraction efficiency; factors such as particle size, surface chemistry, and the hydrodynamic environment of the treatment system must all be optimized in concert to achieve practically meaningful removal rates. The statistical significance of the bead concentration effect, combined with the structural durability demonstrated across reuse cycles, supports the feasibility of the magnetized biopolymer bead concept while identifying surface functionalization and bead design optimization as the most critical areas for future improvement (Divya et al., 2025; Shi et al., 2025).

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that magnetized biopolymer beads composed of sodium alginate embedded with iron-oxide nanoparticles have a statistically significant effect on the extraction of small plastics from low-flow water systems, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Increasing bead concentration from 10 to 40 beads produced a measurable improvement in mean extraction rates, though performance plateaued at concentrations above 20 beads and overall efficiency remained low across all tested concentrations, not exceeding 7.67% even at the highest concentration. The consistency of results across trials confirms that the observed low removal rates reflect the actual adsorption capability of the beads rather than experimental variability. The beads exhibited strong physical and functional stability throughout eight repeated extraction cycles, maintaining structural integrity and 100% magnetic responsiveness without any observable degradation. However, this structural durability was not accompanied by high extraction efficiency, indicating that the primary limitation lies in the beads' adsorption affinity for hydrophobic plastic particles rather than in their mechanical performance.

The key limitation of the current formulation appears to be the hydrophilic-hydrophobic mismatch between the unmodified alginate surface and the predominantly hydrophobic PE, PET, and PP plastics tested. Future research should prioritize surface modification strategies—such as hydrophobic coating, polymer

grafting, or the incorporation of functional ligands with high affinity for specific plastic polymers—to improve binding efficiency. Additionally, investigating the effects of bead size, magnetic field strength, and exposure duration on extraction performance may reveal conditions under which the magnetized alginate bead system achieves practically meaningful removal rates. Testing in more realistic environmental settings, with actual low-flow water bodies and diverse plastic size distributions, will further clarify the system's applicability and scalability. Overall, the results of this study confirm the conceptual feasibility of magnetized biopolymer beads as a low-cost and structurally durable approach for small plastic removal, while establishing that further optimization of adsorption chemistry is necessary before the technology can achieve practical effectiveness for environmental remediation.

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